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Abstract:**Background:** HELLP syndrome is a form of preeclampsia in which endothelial dysfunction is manifested by the activation of coagulation and liver dysfunction, as detected through laboratory tests. 'HELLP' stands for hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, and low platelet count. Tertiary care hospitals are in charge of managing both high-risk pregnancies and the potentially fatal HELLP condition.**Aim:** The aim of this study was to ascertain the mode of presentation, diagnosis, severity, and along with fetomaternal outcome in pregnant women diagnosed with HELLP syndrome at a tertiary healthcare facility.**Materials & Methods:** In the current study, which was conducted at the M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital in Berhampur, 62 people with HELLP syndrome were the participants who were admitted to the wards through the labor room using purposive selection. The researchers selected study participants based on the MISSISSIPPI classification amongst those having either evident preeclampsia or eclampsia features with HELLP syndrome.**Results:** The research indicates that HELLP syndrome was present in most patients (61.3%) between the ages of 21 and 30. There was a wide range of gestational ages, with 27.4% of women diagnosed at 28-32 weeks, 12.9% having 33-34 weeks, 19.3% having 35-36 weeks, 25.8% having 37-38 weeks, 12.9% having 39-40 weeks, and 1.6% being post-term. Pain in the abdomen was the primary complaint of a large number of patients who were brought to the hospital. These patients were from both high and low socioeconomic strata. Fits, headaches, hematuria, visual changes, reduced urination, shortness of breath, weakness, vomiting, leaking or bleeding per vaginum, irritability, head reeling, jaundice, and pedal oedema were some common symptoms.**Conclusion:** To effectively diagnose and treat pregnant women who have HELLP syndrome, it is essential to have a thorough understanding of the sociodemographic factors, gestational age, and presenting difficulties that these women experience. Enhancing treatment options and minimizing the number of unfavourable outcomes by early detection and rigorous monitoring is possible.**Keywords:** Hemolysis; Liver enzymes; Low platelet count; Preeclampsia; Blood pressure; Proteinuria.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The term HELLP syndrome, which stands for hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, and low platelet count, is typically regarded to be a version of severe pre-eclampsia [1]. The HELLP Syndrome was originally described by Pritchard et al in 1954. HELLP syndrome usually occurs between 27 and 36 weeks of gestation. Early identification and treatment are of the utmost importance because of its rapid progression and the possibility of substantial implications for both the mother and the perinatal period [2,3]. Variables including age, parity, socioeconomic level, and educational background might affect how the illness develops and progresses [1,2]. Many of them are misdiagnosed with disorders, like cholecystitis,

oesophagitis, gastritis, hepatitis, viral fever or idiopathic thrombocytopenia etc. In order to prevent the mortalities & morbidities it is essential to identify women who are at greater risk and to provide targeted surveillance and prompt intervention [3,4]. Right upper quadrant pain abdomen or epigastric pain, nausea, vomiting, headaches, and visual issues are some of the nonspecific symptoms that women who have HELLP syndrome may experience when they present themselves. HELLP syndrome is a condition that can be seen in hypertensive or normotensive women [6]; thus, measuring blood pressure is an essential part of the diagnosis process. By monitoring the patterns of blood

pressure in women affected by the disease, it is possible to gain a better understanding of the progression of the problem and the urgency of it [5,6]. Additionally, the Bishop score, a pre-labour scoring system, helps to manage HELLP syndrome since it assists in directing options for delivery time and mode of delivery [7]. Analyzing these parameters in a cohort of pregnant women with HELLP syndrome treated in a tertiary healthcare center may improve clinical awareness, improve diagnosis accuracy, and result in better outcomes for the mother and the child [8,9]. The present study was planned to evaluate the mode of presentation, diagnosis, severity, and along with fetomaternal outcome in pregnant women with HELLP syndrome in a tertiary health-care center.

Materials & Methods

The study was carried out between August 2022 and June 2024 in M.K.C.G. Medical College and Hospital at Berhampur, Odisha. Around, 62 patients were diagnosed cases of HELLP syndrome who were studied for our research. This was prospective observational research that was conducted in a tertiary hospital setting. Patients exhibiting characteristics of HELLP syndrome were admitted through the labour room of the obstetrics and gynecology department. A sampling was carried out on purpose. Those patients who fulfilled the following criteria were chosen for the research. Criteria used for incorporation were:-

1. Patients with a clear diagnosis of pre-eclampsia or eclampsia with HELLP Syndrome based on MISSISSIPPI classification admitted to Labor room. MISSISSIPPI classification include the presence of hemolysis, which may be detected by a peripheral blood smear, as well as biochemical abnormalities such as elevated levels of indirect bilirubin or L.D.H. ($>600\text{IU}$), elevated levels of liver enzymes (AST/ALT > 40), and platelet counts less than 1.5 lakhs.
2. gestational age of >20 weeks and
3. Patients' age should be between 18- 40.

Patients who did not give their consent, patients suffering from any other diseases such as hepatic diseases such as viral hepatitis, hemolytic anemia and other hematological disorders, platelet disorders, chronic hypertension, chronic renal diseases, acute fatty liver of pregnancy, cardiopulmonary diseases or any previous autoimmune disease, and cholecystitis are the patients who are excluded from the study.

During the course of the study, we provided the patient with an explanation of the ethical concerns involved, and we didn't request consent until she or her guardian had a complete comprehension of the study protocol and its contents. We conveyed to the patient that she can withdraw from the research at

any time and that the reason for her withdrawal will not be disclosed.

The Method of Research

After the patient was admitted, we took a brief history that covered the patient's name, age, socioeconomic status, address, and their chief complaints. After determining whether or not the patient needed stabilization, we conducted a comprehensive history. We computed the total number of prenatal checks performed based on whether the case was directly scheduled or referred. We inquired about the date of the L.M.P. based on that information, we computed the E.D.D. additionally, we asked about the history of the current sickness. History of present illness was elicited by asking history of urinary complaints, like increased frequency, burning during micturition, oliguria, or hematuria, as well as premonitory symptoms, including headaches, epigastric discomfort, nausea, vomiting, and visual disturbances. We documented the onset time, the total number of convulsions, the interval between convulsions, the history of any loss of consciousness, and any history of foaming, tongue bite, or passing urine or stool during convulsions whenever there was a history of convulsions in the patient. We inquired about any previous instances of abdominal discomfort, particularly in the epigastric region or in the right upper quadrant area, as well as any history of trauma, per vaginal leakage, or bleeding per vaginum. Inquiries were made on any previous pregnancies, early deliveries, abortions, and intrauterine deaths, as well as any history of gestational hypertension or preeclampsia, as well as any personal, familial, or medical history relating to chronic diseases. Furthermore, we enquired about any medications that were provided previous to the patient's hospitalization, as well as any co-morbidities that were associated with the patient, including diabetes, pre-existing hypertension, renal illness, chronic autoimmune disease, any history of dengue fever, liver diseases, or A.P.L.A. syndrome.

General Examination: We conducted a comprehensive general examination to evaluate the patient's height, weight, nutrition, pallor, icterus oedema, and blood pressure. Additionally, the patient's level of consciousness, temperature, pulse rate, respiration rate, and evidence of tongue bite, heart condition, lung status, and knee jerk were documented. We used the dipstick technique to determine the gradings of proteinuria.

Obstetric Examination: We took note of the uterus's height, contour, and tenderness. The frequency and duration of any uterine contractions noted down. Along with this, we observed lie and presentation of the fetus, the location of the presenting part concerning the brim and the rate & regularity of the

fetal heart. We performed a per-vaginal examination and noted the location, consistency, and dilatation, effacement of the cervix and station of the presenting part. This is also referred to as Bishop's score. We also, examined the pelvic adequacy to determine the mode of termination of the pregnancy. Routine laboratory tests, including Hb%, DC, T.L.C., TPC, peripheral smear, blood grouping and Rh type, E.S.R., random blood sugar, serum urea, creatinine, serum uric acid, LFT, serum sodium, serum potassium, and serum urea coagulation profile & urine routine microscopy for protein and sugar, were done and the results of these tests were analyzed. In every case, we carried out a two-dimensional ultrasound (U.S.G.). In certain instances, such as those suspected of having intrauterine growth restriction (I.U.G.R.), we carried out USG-doppler.

Results

9.7% patients were younger than twenty years old, 61.3%, were between the ages of 21 and 30, and 29%, were between the ages of 31 and 40. Out of the total 62 patients, forty-three patients (69.4%), were referred cases. Majority of the patients (69.4%), belonged to the poor socioeconomic class.

In our study, 24 (38.7%) cases had regular anti-natal check-ups (A.N.C.), whereas 33 (53.2%) patients had irregular A.N.C. Moreover, five individuals (8.1%) didn't do A.N.C. at anyplace.

According to the findings of our research, majority of the patients (67.7%) were primi-gravidas. Within the scope of our research, we found that 27.4% of the total patients, were belonging to very early pre-term period (28-32 weeks), 12.9%, were belonging early pre-term period (33-34 weeks), 19.3%, were belonging to late pre-term period (35-36 weeks), 25.8%, were early term (37-38 weeks) cases, 12.9%, were full-term (39-40 weeks) cases. One patient (1.6%), was a post-term case.

Figure 1: Gestational age, ANC and Referral status Distribution

Amongst the 62 patients, 31 (50%) reported that their primary complaint was abdominal discomfort. There were about 23 patients (37%) who were hospitalized with fits, 20 patients (32.2%) who had headaches, seven patients (11.2%) who had bleeding per vaginum complaint, and six patients (9.6%) who had visual abnormalities. The sense of fetal movements was diminished in 19 (30.6%) patients. a reduction in urination in one individual

(1.6%), shortness of breath in six (9.6%) individuals, and weakness in ten (16.1%) individuals, patients with hematuria were four (6.4%), eight patients (12.9%) had jaundice, ten patients (16.1%) had vomiting, three patients (4.8%) had leaking p/v complaint, one patient (1.6%) was irritable, two patients (3.2%) with head reeling, and twenty-five patients (40.3%) had pedal oedema at the time of admission.

Figure 2: Presenting complaints of the study

Table: 1 Showing Distribution of Patients as Per Their Systolic and Diastolic BP Range at the Time of Admission

SBP	Frequency	Percent
<140	7	11.2%
140-160	27	43.5%
≥160	28	45.1%
Total	62	100%
DBP	Frequency	Percent
<90	17	27.4%
90-110	29	46.7%
≥110	16	25.8%
Total	62	100%

Figure 3: Platelet Levels Distribution & AST Levels

Table 2: Platelet Levels Distribution & AST Levels

Platelet Level	Frequency	Percent
<50,000/ μ L	30	48.4%
50,000-1Lakh/ μ L	27	43.5%
1Lakh-1.5 Lakh/ μ L	5	8.1%
Total	62	100.0%
AST Level	Frequency	Percent
40-70 IU/L	6	9.7%
\geq 70 IU/L	56	90.3%
Total	62	100.0%

Table 3: Alt Levels

ALT Level	Frequency	Percent
40-70 IU/L	16	25.8%
\geq 70 IU/L	46	74.2%
Total	62	100.0%

We observed in our study that, most of the patients had moderate anemia [32 (51.6%)]. The mean Hb of patients was 9.1581 ± 2.3612 . Maximum number of our cases had platelet levels $<50,000/\mu$ L [30 (48.4%)].

The mean value for platelet levels of patients was 55969.3548 ± 27475 . We found that, maximum number of patients had AST Level ≥ 70 IU/L [56 (90.3%)] & the mean AST level of patients was

632.6129 ± 1362 . While ALT Level was ≥ 70 IU/L in majority of our cases [46 (74.2%)]. The mean ALT level of patients was 289.0806 ± 428.3993 .

The mean LDH of patients in the present study was 3775.790 ± 4539.42544 and maximum number of patients [16 (25.8%)] had LDH (in IU/L) >5000 . When the cases were distributed according to MISSISSIPPI classification 50% of them belonged to class-I category.

Figure 4: ALT Levels

Figure 5: LDH Levels

Figure 6: Mississippi Classification

Figure 7: Distribution of new born babies according to birth weight

We observed that, the maximum number of patients had admission to delivery interval of less than 5 hours [35 (56.5%)] while the mean admission to delivery interval (in Hours) of patients was 7.3226±

6.6253. In our study, most of the patients underwent into spontaneous labour [34 (77.3%)]. We also observed that, most of the patients had vaginal delivery [42 (67.7)].

Figure 8: Admission to Delivery Interval

Figure 9: Type of Delivery

Figure 10: Apgar score Distribution

In our study, the mean Apgar Score of patients was $[4.3065 \pm 3.6869]$ and the mean Birth Weight (Kg) of patients was $[2.0258 \pm 0.6613]$. We observed that, the most common over-all neonatal complication was still birth (or intra-uterine deaths) seen in 22 (35.4%) cases, 2nd most common

complication was low birth weight seen in 14 (22.5%) babies.

NICU Admission was required in 23 (57.5%) cases. The most common over-all maternal complication amongst the cases was eclampsia [21 (33.8%)]. Maternal death occurred in 18 (29%)

cases. Other common complications were PPH (24.1%), ARF (16.1%), pulmonary oedema (14.5%), MODS (9.6%), DIC (4.8%) & abruptio (11.2%). About 5 (8.06%) patients recovered without further complications.

In our study, 54 (87.1%) patients required blood component transfusion, 38 (61.3%) patient's required HHDU admission & 10 (16.1%) patients required ICU admission. We observed that, the mean duration of Hospital Stay (Days) of patients was $[5.8226 \pm 3.8048]$.

Figure 11: Demonstrating neonatal complications in our study

Figure 12: Showing maternal complication distribution in our study

Discussion

Since the HELLP syndrome is a condition that rapidly worsens and can lead to significant consequences, it is essential to make an early prediction regarding its likely appearance. This study was carried out in M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital between August 2022 and June 2024 to determine the fetal and maternal outcomes that are linked with HELLP syndrome, as well as the morbidity and mortality related to it. As per the findings of the study, the majority of the patients were between the ages of 21 and 30, with a mean

age of 26.7742 ± 5.0389 years. Most of the admitted patients were referred cases from near-by PHCs, CHCs etc, with irregular anti-natal checkups & were from low socioeconomic background. The majority of patients were primi-gravidas (67.7%). Mean GA in Weeks of patients according to our study was 35.2097 ± 3.2600 .

In the year 2022, according to a study conducted by Kali et al a mean age of 29.6 ± 5.9 years was seen among 104 pregnant women who were diagnosed with HELLP syndrome [10]. They observed that 55.7% of the patients were from rural locations,

indicating they had less access to medical treatment. Shelat et al. conducted a study on foeto-maternal outcome in pregnancies with HELLP syndrome, was during the period between July 2017 and September 2019 where they showed that among the forty instances of HELLP syndrome, 62.5% were unregistered and that the most prevalent age range was between 20–25 years. It was noted by them that patients who were primigravida had a greater likelihood of developing this condition, with a mean gestational age of 36 weeks. [11]. Prospective research was carried out by Bahadur et al. [12] in the state of Andhra Pradesh, India showed that out of the total number of births during the study period which was 5,564, the incidence of HELLP syndrome was 0.7%. According to their study mean age was 23.8 years and majority were between the ages of 20-25. In their research, Kumar et al. [14] found that the age group of 20–25 years was the most prevalent among mothers with HELLP syndrome, accounting for 47.1% of all cases. Furthermore, the average age of mothers was 24.1 ± 4.2 years. Researchers concluded that the mother's gestational age substantially impacts the development of HELLP syndrome. According to Chidanandaiah et al. [13] study, most patients were between 36 and 40 weeks of gestation, with a mean gestational age of 33.6 weeks.

In our study, according to the symptoms that patients exhibited during admission, it was observed that the majority of patients (50%) reported having pain in their abdomen. About 40.3% of patients were diagnosed with pedal oedema at the time of admission. Fits were evident in 37% of the patients, while headaches were present in 32.2%. A reduction in urine (1.6%), shortness of breath (9.6%), weakness (16.1%), hematuria (6.4%), bleeding per vaginum (11.2%), leaking per vaginum (4.8%), head reeling (3.2%), and irritation (1.6%) were some of the other symptoms complained by the patients.

According to the findings of Yimlefack et al. [15], most participants who presented with HELLP syndrome were diagnosed during the postpartum period. Headaches were the most prevalent symptom, accounting for 93.8% of all cases. It was shown that having a history of epigastric discomfort was significantly associated with the development of HELLP syndrome. This correlation was reached using statistical analysis. Siddiqui et al. [16] found that the most prevalent symptom was headache (19.8%), followed by nausea or vomiting (24.6%), R.U.Q. Pain (4.8%) and visual abnormalities in 26% of the cases. Most patients exhibited antepartum onset of HELLP syndrome, as stated by Kumar et al. [14], with headaches being the most prevalent initial symptom, accounting for 56.25 per cent of all cases. Malaise

(fifty per cent), oedema (forty-five per cent), vomiting (20 per cent), and epigastric discomfort (seven point five per cent) were the most common nonspecific symptoms. About, 45.1% patients admitted with systolic blood pressure (S.B.P.) >160 mm hg. The mean SBP of patients was 157.9032 ± 25.4234 . The mean DBP of patients was 98.5161 ± 14.2158 . We observed that, maximum number of patients had Urine albumin 2+ [29 (46.7%)]. The mean Hb of patients was 9.1581 ± 2.3612 . The mean value for platelet levels of patients was 55969.3548 ± 27475 . We found that, maximum number of patients had AST Level ≥ 70 IU/L [56 (90.3%)] and 46 (74.2%) patients had ALT Level ≥ 70 IU/L. In our study, we showed that, maximum number of patients had LDH (in IU/L) >5000 [16 (25.8%)] and the mean LDH of patients was 3775.790 ± 4539.42544 . In our study, we found that, maximum number of our patients belonged to Mississippi class 1 [31 (50.0%)].

Celik et al. [17] found that the average systolic blood pressure was 161.6 mmHg while the average diastolic blood pressure was 98.5 mmHg based on their measurements. Abroug et al. [18] found that individuals with HELLP syndrome had more significant mean proteinuria than those with other syndromes (4.6 ± 3.3 g/day versus 2.2 ± 2.5 g/day; $p = 0.001$). Siddiqui. et al [16] in their study found that anemia was seen in 25 (50%) of the HELLP syndrome cases. Kumar. et al [14] distributed their patients as per the admission parameters & found that the mean platelet count was $0.39 \pm 0.07/\mu\text{L}$ in Class 1, in Class 2 it was $0.88 \pm 0.21/\mu\text{L}$, in Class 3 the mean platelet value was $1.02 \pm 0.16/\mu\text{L}$. Shelat P.M. et al [11] in their study observed that most cases were falling into class II of Mississippi classification (45%) and 87.5% cases were of complete HELLP syndrome according to Tennessee classification.

We observed that, the mean admission to delivery interval (in Hours) of patients was 7.3226 ± 6.6253 . In our study maximum number of patients had spontaneous onset of labour [34 (77.3%)] and vaginal delivery was the mode of delivery in 42 (67.7%) cases. Out of 40 live births, 25 (40.3%) of the delivered babies of HELLP cases had Apgar Score 7-10 but 8 (12.9%) babies had Apgar Score between 0-3. We found that, the mean Birth weight (Kg) of babies was $[2.0258 \pm 0.6613]$. In our study, the most common neonatal complication was still birth (IUD) of babies seen in 22 (35.4%) cases. Other neonatal complications were LBW (22.5%), pre-maturity (13%), neonatal death (11.9%), FGR (3.2%) and RDS (20.9%). About, 23 (57.5%) of the delivered babies required NICU admission. We found that, according to our study most common maternal complication was eclampsia [21 (33.8%)]. Other maternal complications seen in our cases were ARF (16.1%), pulmonary oedema (14.5%),

abruptio (11.2%), PPH (24.1%), MODS (9.6%), DIC (4.8%). Maternal death occurred in 18 (29%) cases. In our study, 54(87.1%) patients required blood component transfusion. About 38 (61.3%) patients required HHU admission and 10(16.1%) required ICU admission. While, the mean Duration of Hospital Stay (Days) of our cases was [5.8226± 3.8048].

Yimlefact et al. [15] observed that concerning delivery, 62.5% (10) of their HELLP syndrome patients were delivered by caesarean section, while 37.5% (6) were delivered vaginally. Bahadur. et al [12] in their study showed that 50% of their cases had vaginal delivery & 50% cases underwent caesarean section. Induction was done in 22 (55%) cases of their study. Out of which, 11 (50%) cases had failed induction and underwent caesarean section. Kaur A.P. et al [19] showed in their study that perinatal mortality rate amongst the patients of HELLP syndrome was 43.7% while maternal death occurred in 12.7% of partial & 75% of complete HELLP cases. Most common fetal complication their study was IUGR. Bahadur. et al [12] observed in their study that 47.5% (n=19) of neonates needed NICU admission. Shelat P.M.et al [11] stated that most common maternal complication in their study were acute renal failure (27.5%) and DIC (22.5%). In their study, 78% required blood products transfusion and despite care in ICU and HDU there were 12% maternal deaths and 20% perinatal deaths. Patil. et al [20] study showed that, placental abruption (35.29 %) was most common complication noted, followed by postpartum hemorrhage (29.41 %). Kali. et al [10] study showed that the rate of admission to intensive care unit (ICU) was 22.1% (n=23).

Conclusion:

Illiteracy and ignorance of patients leads to poor compliance in antenatal care in peripheral area and ultimately resulting in late diagnosis. Regular antenatal check-up henceforth plays a major role. We concluded that, managing HELLP syndrome requires a tertiary care hospital as it is one of the dreadful obstetric complications which multidisciplinary team needs approach.

Early detection, prompt referral, better transport facility, appropriate and timely intervention, availability of life saving facilities like mechanical ventilators, dialysis equipment and blood products like FFP, platelets, packed cell transfusion at tertiary care centers and rapid treatment can be aided by the early identification of high-risk patients through demographic profiles, thorough monitoring of symptoms, and watchful analysis of clinical data.

This can help to reduce the number of bad outcomes for both mothers and the newborns. Medical professionals need to enhance their

treatment strategy by customizing therapies more precisely to the requirements of women with HELLP syndrome, ultimately leading to improved patient outcomes.

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